

Ecosystem and Landuse Policy Group (ELPEG) Bulletin - October 2022

Introduction

Welcome to this, our first ELPEG bulletin of the 2022-2027 RESAS strategic research programme. The aim of this bulletin is to provide policy makers with updates on the research on biodiversity that is happening within the strategic research programme. The bulletin will cover work from Topic D4 (Biodiversity) and the biodiversity elements within the air pollution Topic (D1).

For our first bulletin we have provided one-page summaries of the seven projects within the biodiversity topic and the one project within the air pollution topic that covers the impacts of pollution on biodiversity. Our aim is to update these summaries as the projects progress, producing new bulletins every six months.

We welcome your feedback on this new style of bulletin and if you have comments please do either provide them at the ELPEG meeting or contact Ruth.Mitchell@hutton.ac.uk

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Introduction to Theme D and how to find out more about the work on Soils, Water and Natural Capital

Theme D - Natural Resources is one of five themes in the Strategic Research Programme. The others are A Plant and Animal Health, B Sustainable Food System and Supply, C Human impacts on the Environment and E Rural Futures.

Within Theme D there are five Topics D1 Air Quality, D2 Water (inc Flooding), D3 Soils, D4 Biodiversity, D5 Natural Capital. ELPEG and ELSEG will largely focus on D4 Biodiversity and the biodiversity work in D1 Air Quality.

Each Topic has their own mechanisms for engagement with policy and with stakeholders:

D1 – Air pollution

The project on ammonia emissions is working specifically with the CAFS2 (Cleaner Air for Scotland Strategy) Agriculture and Environment Working Group (AEWG) and the project on particulates with the CAFS2 Domestic Emissions Working Group (DEWG). The project on air pollution and biodiversity is engaging with ELPEG and ELSEG. Contact Andrea.Britton@hutton.ac.uk for further details.

D2 - Water (inc Flooding)

This Topic has established an engagement group with SG policy (teams working on Water and Environment, Flooding, Water Industry team, Drinking Water Quality) and a wider engagement group (including NatureScot, SEPA, Councils, Scottish Water, NHS, land managers and communities). A summary of the projects in this Topic is also circulated with this ELPEG bulletin called "RESAS Strategic Research Programme Topic D2 water - Summary of projects (June 2022)". Contact Mark.Wilkinson@hutton.ac.uk for further details.

D3 - Soils

The engagement will cover work in the Topic, Underpinning Capacity and other Topics in Theme D and with Themes A, B and C. It is envisaged that policy and public engagement will be delivered through the underpinning capacity (JHI-UNC-9) with other stakeholders engaged through the new 'Soils Network' developed in this topic. The Soils Network will include representatives of LEAF, Soil Association, Zero Waste Scotland, SAOS, NFU Scotland, AHDB. A copy of the newsletter produced by this Topic "The Soil Sentinel" is attached. Contact Eric.Paterson@hutton.ac.uk or Kenneth.Loades@hutton.ac.uk for further details.

D5 - Natural Capital

A series of specific end user groups has been set up, one for each project in the topic. These involve, amongst others, SG, ONS, NatureScot, Defra, SEPA and the Office of the Chief Economic Advisor. A summary of the projects within this Topic is also circulated with this ELPEG bulletin called "2022-27 D5 Natural Capital 6 x projects". Contact Kerry.Waylen@hutton.ac.uk for further details.

Nitrogen impacts in natural ecosystems

Lead PI: **Andrea Britton** (andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

To improve understanding of the impacts of nitrogen deposition on Scottish natural ecosystems in the context of a changing climate, providing evidence on how natural ecosystems are changing, what is driving this change and how best to manage and protect them.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

1. Review of nitrogen and climate impacts on Scottish ecosystems

Contact: andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk

We are currently reviewing the literature to assess the state of knowledge on the interactive effects of nitrogen deposition and climate change on biodiversity and function of Scottish ecosystems. The review will inform 'risk assessments' for interactive nitrogen-climate effects to be used in modelling.

2. Cross habitat analysis of interactive effects of nitrogen deposition and climate change on spatial and temporal vegetation change

Contact: andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk

Existing datasets describing vegetation in Scotland will be used to investigate nitrogen-climate effects across a wide range of habitats.

3. Nitrogen and climate impacts on above and below ground biodiversity in alpine ecosystems

Contact: andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk

Starting in 2023, we will revisit long term vegetation plots 50 years after the first sampling to examine how nitrogen and climate change are affecting plant and soil biodiversity in alpine habitats.

4. Nitrogen and climate impacts on woodland ectomycorrhizal communities

Contact: andy.taylor@hutton.ac.uk

Using data from the National Biodiversity Network and new data collected from birch, oak and pine forests across Scotland, we are investigating how nitrogen deposition and climate affect woodland fungal communities.

5. Impacts of nitrogen climate interactions on ecosystem function

Contact: andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk

Using long-term (20+ years) experimental plots in alpine heath we are investigating how warming and nitrogen additions affect carbon and nutrient stocks, nutrient cycling and above and belowground biodiversity.

6. Modelling of nitrogen climate interactions

Contact: mike.rivington@hutton.ac.uk

Starting in 2024, we will be using data gained from all studies to model risks to Scottish ecosystems from interactive impacts of nitrogen deposition and climate change.

7. Review of potential for mitigation of nitrogen impacts on Scottish ecosystems and metrics of success

Contact: andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk

We are reviewing the literature to assess the evidence on success of management interventions to mitigate nitrogen impacts on Scottish ecosystems, and to determine appropriate metrics of nitrogen impact and recovery.

8. Experimental trial of nitrogen mitigation methods and indicators

Contact: robin.pakeman@hutton.ac.uk

Starting 2023 we will trial a potential method for nitrogen impact mitigation in a Scottish ecosystem, with the experimental design guided by the review of mitigation methods.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- Sampling of soil carbon and nutrient stocks in the long-term alpine heath study is complete

People and Nature

Lead PI: **Katherine (Kate) Irvine** (kate.irvine@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

Identify and evaluate interventions, approaches and processes to facilitate the transformative change of how Scotland's biodiversity is framed, valued, managed and governed, and how to harness and more equitably distributed the associated benefits.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

For further information on any of the objectives below please contact Kate.Irvine@hutton.ac.uk

- 1. Nature and Economy:** Explore nature-economy relations and the implications of different framings for managing nature.

Identified the 'Life Framework of Values' as a way to frame the discourse on nature-economy relationships. A protocol for the discourse analysis is being developed.
- 2. Enabling inclusivity in biodiversity narratives:** Identify narrative and approaches which are usually outside of biodiversity research, and develop and evaluate audio-visual and interactive narrative tools and techniques to better enable their productive engagement for transformative change.

Undertaking review of marginalized biodiversity narratives and online platforms. Ethics application submitted and stakeholder interviewees compiled.
- 3. Enabling transformative biodiversity research and change:** Examine how novel management interventions and transformative research can enable more diverse, sustainable and just futures.

Fieldwork protocol being developed. Strathmore wildlife cluster and POBAS farmers identified as possible participants.
- 4. Values:** To understand the different societal, economic and biological values associated with biodiversity within nature conservation and farming practices, and how these values may be leveraged and changed with transformative research.

Designing a research plan with intention to align development of values framework with WP1.
- 5. Harnessing Green / Blue Infrastructure for people and nature:** Focusing on how to measure and develop green-blue infrastructure for multiple benefits through exploration of the impact of different types of interventions.

Fieldwork for digital stories of impact developed, ethics approved, pilot interviews underway.

Identifying the causes of biodiversity change with specific references to the IPBES drivers

Lead PI: **Robin Pakeman** (robin.pakeman@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

The aim of this project is to identify how the "IPBES drivers", specifically climate change, land use change, pollution and invasive species, affect key parts of Scotland's biodiversity.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

1. Global change impacts on sustainable upland land use

Contact: robin.pakeman@hutton.ac.uk

We are continuing our work on the Long-term Glen Finglas grazing experiment but extending it to assess how spatial and temporal variation in habitat structure affect nesting density in meadow pipits. Early analysis shows a link between vegetation biomass and nesting density.

2. Collective landscape management of farmland biodiversity

Contact: graham.begg@hutton.ac.uk

We are investigating the potential of the Farmer Cluster approach as a tool to reverse biodiversity loss by improving farmland management at landscape scales.

3. Using long-term aphid monitoring data to assess drivers of biodiversity change

Contact: ali.karley@hutton.ac.uk

We are analysing Scottish trends in aphid species abundance, composition and diversity and assessing how different drivers such as changes in climate, pesticide use and in land use are contributing to their long-term dynamics.

4. Using Scotland's Caledonian forest as a model system to assess impacts of major climate drivers

Contact: alison.hester@hutton.ac.uk, jenni.sockan@hutton.ac.uk

We are using our unique experimental "sapling bank" of native Scots pine to assess which provenances are likely to cope better with future drought scenarios to assess both at risk areas and to inform future planting strategies.

5. Assessing potential effect of chemical pollution on the wild Scottish salmon

Contact: zulin.zhang@hutton.ac.uk

We are assessing how Endocrine Disrupting Compounds are distributed in aquatic systems and how they bio-magnify through the food chain and bio-accumulate in salmon with population and ecosystem impacts.

6. Improved technology to track invasive non-native pathogens and their effects on ecosystems

Contact: david.cooke@hutton.ac.uk

This research will exploit novel approaches to use environmental DNA (eDNA) to catalogue biodiversity via metabarcoding and use it to examine discover microbial plant pathogens that threaten biodiversity.

7. Impact Assessment of Invasive Non-Native Species

Contact: michaela.roberts@hutton.ac.uk; ruth.mitchell@hutton.ac.uk

We will develop a risk assessment approach for non-native plant pests and pathogens that identifies habitats at greatest risk because of a lack of functional redundancy. We will also improve the understanding of socio-economic implications of establishment and spread of INNS in Scotland.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- [Glen Finglas – A synthesis for policy](#)
- [DNA Metabarcoding and Isolation by Baiting Complement Each Other in Revealing Phytophthora Diversity in Anthropized and Natural Ecosystems](#)
- [NSA Sheep Event 2022 Seminar 2: Is grassland our salvation for carbon capture and nature recovery?](#)

Scotland's biodiversity: People, data and monitoring

Lead PI: **Jenni Stockan** (jenni.stockan@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

The aim of this project is to help protect Scotland's share of global biodiversity by optimising people's skills, data, and technologies to ensure effective recording and monitoring techniques and data flows.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

1. Creating a Scottish biodiversity inventory

Contact: andy.taylor@hutton.ac.uk

We are investigating how a more comprehensive and balanced inventory of Scottish biodiversity can be created. Working closely with the NBN, we will identify major knowledge gaps in our current inventory and potential reasons for their existence so that we can develop possible solutions. We will use case studies of functionally important groups to assess how distinctive our biodiversity is in a global context.

2. Improved reporting

Contact: kit.macleod@hutton.ac.uk/robin.pakeman@hutton.ac.uk

We are developing novel ways of improving the reporting of species trends and their relationship with habitats. We are also exploring infrastructure improvements that could enhance State of Nature reporting and biological recording data flows.

3. Genetic diversity of mountain hares and their capacity to adapt

Contact: scott.newey@hutton.ac.uk

We are developing a non-invasive genetic sampling method to assess the use of genetic markers in the Scottish mountain hare. This will provide the tools to quantify population size, genetic diversity, genetic mixing and introgression/hybridisation within the population, allowing us to develop further tools for monitoring difficult to survey species cost effectively, and enable increased capacity and expertise in wildlife genetics.

4. Oceanic-alpine soil biodiversity

Contact: andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk

We are expanding our pilot citizen science project, which has already found fungi new to science, to collect soil samples from all 282 Munros in Scotland to characterise alpine soil biodiversity. This will significantly increase our evidence base of Scottish natural assets in our mountain landscapes and further highlight the uniqueness of these habitats.

5. Monitoring approaches for outcomes focussed interventions

Contact: cathy.hawes@hutton.ac.uk

We are working with NatureScot to test, validate and extend a set of farmer/crofter led monitoring protocols that have been developed through Phases 1 and 2 (2020-22) of NatureScot's POBAS (Piloting an Outcomes Based Approach in Scotland) project. Thus far, we have trialled field margin score cards and provided feedback on modifications required for use by farmers.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-scotland-highlands-islands-62150479>
- Partner in BIOSCAN project: improving DNA-based biomonitoring in the UK
- Article on indicators in *In Practice*, the membership publication of the Chartered Institute of Ecology and Environmental Management

Habitat management and restoration

Lead PI: **Scott Newey** (scott.newey@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

To gain biodiversity in moorland and woodland habitats through evidence-based land management and restoration to maximise benefits to society.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

- 1 How can public and private sector investors, at low risk, restore woodland habitats for the most multiple benefits to society in addition to increasing natural carbon capture and biodiversity, and what land is available for this?**

Contact: matt.hare@hutton.ac.uk

We are reviewing and developing the evidence base on the flow of benefits to society and communities, as well as risks (related to climate change and investor behaviour), associated with restoring and expanding woodland habitats. We are adopting an interdisciplinary approach that combines socio-economic data analysis, participatory community-based assessment and socio-biophysical modelling. Literature review, assessment of available data and biophysical modelling are all underway.

- 2 What is the impact of Muirburn on nature and how does this impact compare to mechanical removal of vegetation?**

Contact: scott.newey@hutton.ac.uk

We will investigate the occurrence of wildfire in relation to the distribution and intensity of muirburn, and set up experiments to assess and compare the effects of muirburn and mechanical cutting of heather on soil characteristics. To better understand the effects of muirburn on below ground ecology we are using soil nematode community data, a recognised proxy indicator of soil function, to assess the effect of temperature and distance from fire on soil nematode community composition.

- 3 How do our ancient woodlands function and how successful is woodland restoration?**

Contact: andy.taylor@hutton.ac.uk

We will assess a) change in ecosystem services and properties when conifer plantations are established on ancient woodland sites, and b) how successful restoration is to restore these sites. Focus is on soil functional biodiversity. We have now identified six study sites representing a range from existing plantation, felled and recovering sites and old growth, oak woodland. We have established monitoring plots within these six habitats with seven replicates within each. Soil samples have been collected for edaphic biodiversity and soil characterisation, and nutrient probes and decomposition assays have been installed within each monitoring plot.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- Fieldwork and data collection has begun

Protected areas to tackle biodiversity loss now, and for the future

Lead PI: **Ruth Mitchell** (ruth.mitchell@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

To improve our understanding of how to design effective protected area networks against a backdrop of rapid environmental change and how to measure the success of protected areas

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

1. Can applying a seascape approach to marine protection benefit biodiversity protection and improve fishery sustainability?

Contact: neil.burns@sruc.ac.uk

Our work is focused on Loch Eriboll and Little Loch Broom where we are deploying stereo-video cameras to sample fish abundance and community structure allowing us to build up a map of the seabed.

2. How can protected areas ensure that threatened genetic diversity is safeguarded

Contact: jenni.stockan@hutton.ac.uk

For this work we are utilizing our Scot's Pine common garden experiment with pine trees grown from known mothers from 21 protected Caledonian forests in 3 replicated sites across different bioclimatic zones. We are reviewing the role of genetic diversity in determining pine responses to climatic variability over decadal+ timescales.

3. Can we identify refugia for species which are unlikely to disperse quickly in the face of a changing climate

Contact: c.ellis@rbge.ac.uk

We are reviewing the literature to assess how microtopography can provide climate refugia within protected areas. We will then focus on Atlantic rainforests as a case study and have so far deployed data-loggers across three target NNRs.

4. How do we measure the success of our protected areas?

Contact: ruth.mitchell@hutton.ac.uk

We are utilizing long-term vegetation data sets from 1970's-2000's to assess differences in vegetation change inside and outside protected areas, across a range of habitats within Scotland.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- [Long-term multisite Scots pine trial, Scotland: mother tree, cone and seed phenotypes, 2007.](#)
- [Long-term multisite Scots pine trial, Scotland: field phenotypes, 2013-2020.](#)
- [Long-term multisite Scots pine trial, Scotland: nursery phenotypes, 2007-2011.](#)

Assessing the impact of changing migratory patterns, population size and diversity of greylag geese on livestock and public health

Lead PI: **Eleanor Watson** (eleanor.watson@moredun.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

To investigate the microbial risks associated with rapidly expanded resident and migratory greylag goose populations on Orkney, and assess economic, conservation and social impacts.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

1. Investigate transmission of *Cryptosporidium parvum*, *Campylobacter* and antimicrobial resistance between geese, calves and cattle and the wider environment

Contacts: clare.hamilton@moredun.ac.uk (*Cryptosporidium*), eleanor.watson@moredun.ac.uk (*Campylobacter*) and nuno.silva@moredun.ac.uk (antimicrobial resistance)

Strategies for farm sampling have been reviewed and methodologies for recovery of viable bacteria have been optimised. Study farm recruitment is underway with support from the Orkney Goose Management Group.

2. Development of molecular tools to genotype geese

Contact: keith.ballingall@moredun.ac.uk

Methods for DNA extraction are under review, and goose blood and faecal samples have been archived as a resource to optimise techniques and validate approaches. Samples from goose populations on Iceland have been collected by our collaborator at the Rif Field Station, shipped and archived.

3. Engage with stakeholder groups to inform project progression, assess impact of findings and highlight successful approaches for related studies

Contact: eleanor.watson@moredun.ac.uk and beth.wells@moredun.ac.uk

The project has been outlined to members of the Orkney Goose Management Group and summary documents have been prepared for wider circulation amongst stakeholders in Orkney to raise awareness of the project.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- Article within the Orcadian newspaper focusing on previous findings and planned research (“Research to start into goose disease threat”, September 2022)
- A report for policy contacts has been circulated describing pilot study findings
- The project plan has been presented to researchers within the University of Saskatchewan, Canada (“Antimicrobial Resistance and Zoonosis within Scottish Wildlife Populations”)

Seeking multiple benefits from natural carbon stores in the uplands

Lead PI: **Davy McCracken** (davy.mccracken@sruc.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

Explore the relationship between carbon storage, biodiversity conservation and flood mitigation to detect synergies and trade-offs and identify land management practices that optimise the benefits derived

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

Our work is focused on SRUC's Kirkton and Auchtertyre farms where we are focusing on carbon storage (in the soil, and vegetation), biodiversity conservation and flood mitigation.

1. **Ground-truth existing maps of carbon storage potential and flood mitigation using on the ground surveys and environmental sensors to monitor rainfall and water flow, and expand the spatial coverage of these maps to include all predominant habitats on the estate.**

Soil depth measurements trialed across a subset of lowland sampling sites and methodology adapted

2. **Supplement existing biodiversity datasets, through the collection of new biodiversity data to expand spatial coverage to cover all predominant habitats present on the farm, and implement innovative approaches to monitor biodiversity (e.g., acoustic sensors and camera traps)**

Audiomoth acoustic loggers deployed at the fourteen lowland sites for three days during August 2022, specifically focusing on bat detection. Pollinator transects carried out across all lowland (45 transects) and upland sites (36 transects) during July and August.

3. **Trial scorecards developed under NatureScot's project Piloting an Outcomes Based Approach (POBAS) in Scotland and the NatureScot Civtech Challenge Habitat Quality app to determine how effective proposed scorecards are as indicators of wider biodiversity**

Iceni-earth habitat score card app (for POBAS) tested at Kirkton. Report produced and sent to NatureScot

4. **Quantify the relationships between metrics relating to carbon storage, biodiversity conservation and flood mitigation to identify synergies and trade-offs between these key ecosystem services, and identify land management practices that optimise these multiple benefits**

To complete in Year 4

5. **Utilise data from Kirkton and Auchtertyre farms to create spatial models of carbon storage, biodiversity conservation potential and flood mitigation for part of the upper River Tay catchment, and collect additional data to ground-truth these at several sites, to test the scalability of findings generated during this study**

To complete in Year 5

Recent highlights or outputs:

- [The use of sensors in this project is forming a case study for a separate Scottish Government funded Knowledge Transfer Innovation Fund project.](#)
- [A stakeholder engagement event \[involving colleagues from SEPA, NatureScot and Loch Lomond & The Trossachs National Park\] was held in May 2022](#)
- [The rationale behind the project formed the basis of an SRUC display at the Highland Show in June 2022](#)